

My dearest and much beloved John,

Congratulations on coming of age!

I am sending to you my best wishes of health and happiness, and lots of interesting work, many good friends, able students, great artists to work with and much, much love!

I will always remember our concerts and the joy of making music together!

Thank you for these moments of happiness when I was losing myself in music.

You are a great musician, a brilliant pianist and a very, very good friend!

May God grant you happiness in all your beginnings.

Always yours,

Elena Obraztsova